

Test Case 2: Denial of Service Attack

Test Case 1: Key Reinstallation Attack

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
[00:00:05] 20869/10303727 keys tested (3860.64 k/s)
Time left: 44 minutes, 23 seconds 0.20%
KEY FOUND! [ 12345678 ]

Master Key : 21 AE ED 25 03 DC 99 DF E6 56 95 F4 F2 64 E5 41
             5C AC 28 7F 76 FD 63 FB 8B 22 C7 84 DD 73 A9 49

Transient Key : 81 14 5F D8 C6 03 D4 AC 6C BE 8B CD B4 63 57 5C
                0C E1 0C 9C 52 F1 57 C5 7B 6F 06 96 C4 84 AB E2
                AS 05 2B FF 01 18 B2 A1 25 86 00 14 00 52 95 09
                83 28 55 EE 70 A3 27 A9 CD DC 60 80 6C 11 C1 11

EAPOL HMAC : 1D 22 CE 96 52 27 76 44 CA 9E 91 91 BC 0C 80 AD
```

Fig.1 Test Case 1 on WPA2

```
kali@kali:~$ sudo aircrack-ng -b A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE netgearwpa3-01.cap -w rockyou.txt
Reading packets, please wait ...
Opening netgearwpa3-01.cap
Read 2734 packets.
1 potential targets

Unsupported key version 0 encountered.
May be WPA3 - not yet supported.
zsh: IOT instruction sudo aircrack-ng -b A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE netgearwpa3-01.cap -w rockyou.txt
```

Fig.2 Test Case 1 on WPA3

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the interface of Aircrack-ng during an attempt to crack the captured handshake file.

- In Figure 1, Aircrack-ng successfully retrieves the WPA2 router password. This indicates that WPA2 is vulnerable to the Key Reinstallation Attack (KRACK), as it allows the attacker to reinstall a key by exploiting a weakness in the 4-way handshake process.
- Figure 2, however, shows that Aircrack-ng is unable to crack the WPA3 handshake. This is due to WPA3's use of the Simultaneous Authentication of Equals (SAE) algorithm, which mitigates the risk of KRACK by ensuring that each session handshake uses a unique and robust encryption key. As a result, WPA3 demonstrates strong resistance to the same attack.

This test case highlights the significant security improvement that WPA3 provides over WPA2, particularly in defending against Key Reinstallation Attacks..

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
21:38:22 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:22 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:23 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:23 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:24 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:24 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:25 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:25 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:26 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:26 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:27 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:27 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:28 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:28 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:29 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:29 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:30 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:30 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
21:38:31 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
write failed: Network is down
wi_write(): Network is down
```

Fig.3 Test Case 2 on WPA2

```
kali@kali:~$ aircrack-ng 1.7
22:00:00 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:01 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:01 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:02 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:02 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:03 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:03 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:04 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:04 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:05 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:05 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:06 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:06 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:07 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:07 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:08 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:08 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:09 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:09 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:10 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:10 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:11 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
22:00:11 Sending DeAuth (code 7) to broadcast -- BSSID: [A0:04:60:7A:E7:FE]
```

Fig.4 Test Case 2 on WPA3

Figure 3 and Figure 4 demonstrate the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack using Aireplay-ng on router X.

- Figure 3 shows that the DoS attack successfully disrupts the network on the WPA2-protected router. This indicates that WPA2 lacks sufficient protection against DoS attacks, making it vulnerable to such disruptions.
- In contrast, Figure 4 illustrates that the same DoS attack is ineffective against the WPA3-protected router. This is due to WPA3's implementation of the Frame Management Protocol (FMP), which provides enhanced protection against DoS attacks by validating management frames and preventing malicious interference.

This test case underscores the improved resilience of WPA3 networks against Denial of Service attacks, whereas WPA2 remains susceptible to such vulnerabilities.

Test Case 3: Denial of Service Attack on Client Y

Fig.5 Test Case 3 on WPA2

Fig.6 Test Case 3 on WPA3

Figure 5 and **Figure 6** highlight the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack targeting client Y while connected to router X.

- **Figure 5** demonstrates that client Y, when connected to a WPA2-protected network, is vulnerable to the DoS attack. The network connection is disrupted, showing WPA2's inability to adequately protect clients from such attacks.
- **Figure 6** shows that when client Y is connected to a WPA3-protected network, the DoS attack is unsuccessful. This is due to WPA3's Frame Management Protocol (FMP), which enhances security by preventing the disruption of client connections during a DoS attack.

This test case further emphasizes the superiority of WPA3 in safeguarding network clients from Denial of Service attacks, compared to WPA2.

Test Case 4: Denial of Service Attack on Client Z

Fig.7 Test Case 4 on WPA2

Fig.8 Test Case 4 on WPA3

Figure 7 and **Figure 8** depict the results of a Denial of Service (DoS) attack directed at client Z while connected to router X.

- **Figure 7** illustrates that client Z, when connected to a WPA2-secured network, is vulnerable to the DoS attack, with the connection being disrupted. This highlights the security limitations of WPA2 against such attacks.
- **Figure 8** demonstrates that when client Z is connected to a WPA3-secured network, the DoS attack is unsuccessful. WPA3's Frame Management Protocol (FMP) prevents interference with the client's network connection, ensuring robust protection against DoS attacks.

This test case reinforces the enhanced security provided by WPA3 compared to WPA2, particularly in protecting clients from Denial of Service attacks.

Test Case 5: Network Sniffing Attack on Router X

Fig.9 Test Case 5 on WPA2

Fig.10 Test Case 5 on WPA3

Figure 9 and Figure 10 illustrate the outcomes of a Network Sniffing attack on router X.

- **Figure 9** shows that when router X is secured with WPA2, the network is vulnerable to sniffing attacks. The attacker can capture and decrypt data transmitted over the network, exposing sensitive information.
- **Figure 10** demonstrates that when router X is secured with WPA3, the Network Sniffing attack fails. This is due to WPA3's forward secrecy, which uses a stronger encryption algorithm to ensure that even if data is intercepted, it cannot be decrypted by the attacker.

This test highlights the significant improvement in encryption and privacy provided by WPA3 over WPA2, especially in preventing network sniffing attacks.

Test Case 6: Network Port Scanning on Router X

Fig.11 Test Case 6 on WPA2

Fig.12 Test Case 6 on WPA3

Figure 11 and Figure 12 present the outcomes of a Network Port Scanning attack on router X.

- **Figure 11** shows that router X using WPA2 is vulnerable to a Network Port Scanning attack. The scan successfully identifies open ports, which could be exploited by an attacker to gain access to the network or launch further attacks.
- **Figure 12** demonstrates that when router X is secured with WPA3, the Network Port Scanning attack fails. This is due to WPA3's enhanced client isolation feature, which restricts access between devices on the same network, preventing the attacker from detecting open ports.

This test emphasizes WPA3's superior protection against port scanning attacks compared to WPA2, providing an additional layer of security through improved network isolation.